

THE INITIAL DEVELOPMENT OF AN EXPERT SYSTEM FOR DESIGNING
COMPOSITE MATERIAL WING STRUCTURES

J. L. Chen, W.-C. Hwang* and S.-H. Sun
Department of Mechanical Engineering
National Cheng Kung University
Tainan, TAIWAN 70101, Republic of China
*Chung Shan Institute of Science and Technology
Lung-Tan, TAIWAN, Republic of China

ABSTRACT

This paper describes an initial implementation of an expert system for designing composite material wing structures. Currently, this expert system contains two subsystems for composite material selection and preliminary configuration arrangement of wing structures. The overall architecture of this system and the structure of the knowledge base, knowledge representation, and inference engine used in this system are presented. The present capabilities of this expert system are demonstrated with example.

KEYWORDS: Composites; Expert System; Wing Structural Design; Design Methodology; Material Selection.

1. INTRODUCTION

The increasing use of advanced structural composites in aircraft, missile systems and space structures has been well documented, and continues to receive industry-wide attention. This situation has produced a need for structural designers to

be familiar with the property of composite materials and the knowledge of designing composite material structures in order to design structures properly. The traditional approach for the transfer of those data and knowledge has been in the form of design guides and handbooks (1). Many computer aided design programs and material data base systems were developed to aid the structural designer performing the design task. However, they can not provide the intelligent knowledge to aid the structural designer doing decision making during the design process. Recently, the rapidly developing technology of expert systems provides a useful solution to this problem (2-4).

This paper describes the initial development of a consultative expert system for designing composite material wing structures. The aim of this expert system is to bring the special knowledge about designing composite material wing structures into the computer and to aid the structural designer in designing best composite material wing structures. The preliminary phases of this system include the composite material selection and structural configuration arrangement. The overall architecture of this expert system is illustrated. The structure of knowledge base, knowledge representation, and inference engine used in this system are presented. The present capabilities of this expert system are discussed and demonstrated with example.

2. DESIGN OF COMPOSITE MATERIAL WING STRUCTURES

As illustrated in Figure 1, the design of composite material wing structures may be viewed as a sequence of steps that must be performed to obtain an optimum design. Based on the design

requirements which was defined by the designer, the first step during design process is the selecting of composite material. Next step is the design of wing structures. This step contains the decision making of cross-sectional configuration, structural type, and dimensions. The verification of the

Figure 1. Flowchart of the design of composite material wing structures.

predicted failure mode with the results of structural analysis was the third step. Finally, the design refinement was performed to modify the proposed design if the proposed design was unsatisfaction.

3. THE EXPERT SYSTEM

The developing expert system is presently operational on an PC-AT compatible personal computer. Currently, the principal source of expert knowledge is the prior experience of domain expert. This information was presented and discussed with a domain expert to validate its inclusion. The other principal source of expert knowledge was the documentation available in the literature, such as books, design guidelines, and product catalogs.

3.1 Architecture of the Expert System The current structure of this expert system is illustrated in Figure 2. It contains a data base, a data base management system (DBASE-III-PLUS), a knowledge base, an inference engine (PC-PLUS), and a user interface facility for the knowledge collection and user consultation tasks.

3.2 Data Base Management System A data base for collecting the properties of various composite materials was developed within this data base management system. The current structure of this data base management system is illustrated as Figure 3. Through the operation of this system, the designer can browse or modify the data of composite material properties within this data base.

3.3 Organization of Knowledge Base The current organization of the knowledge base for composite material wing

Figure 2. Architecture of the expert system.

Figure 3. Structure of the data base management system.

structural design is shown in Figure 4. Knowledge bases are organized in terms of frame trees. At the top level is the "MAINFRAME" root frame which contains the meta-rules to choose the performing tasks. Two subframes, "SELECT_MATERIAL" and "STRUCTURAL_COMPONENT", which attached to the root frame represent the material selection subsystem and wing structural design subsystem, respectively.

Figure 4. Knowledge base organization of the expert system.

3.4 Knowledge Representation In this system, knowledge was represented by the frame-based knowledge representation scheme. Frames are used to partition knowledge into distinct groups of rules and parameters. This system provides for a type of inheritance in which subframes inherit rules and parameters from their parent frames. An example of a rule in the BY_PROPERTY subframe is the following:

Rule 111:

IF: FIBER_REQUIREMENT = TENSILE_MODULUS
AND TENSILE_MODULUS = MODERATE

THEN: FIBER =S-GLASS CF 50

where "CF 50" means certainty factor = 50.

3.5 Inference Engine Both forward and backward chaining reasoning methods with certainty factor capability were used in this expert system. The inference engine in "PC-PLUS" has twelve special functions to deal with the "DBASE-III-PLUS" system for operating information in data base.

3.6 Illustrative Example For composite material selection task, this expert system offers two approaches, application area approach and requirement of material properties approach, for the designer, as shown in Figure 5. In the first approach, the expert system will enter the "BY_PURPOSE" subframe and suggest the suitable material based on the designer's input information. Then, the designer can enter the data base to find all the details of material properties. As for the second approach, the expert system will infer suitable fiber and matrix based on the requirement of material properties separately, as shown in Figure 6. After the expert system prompt results, the designer can enter the data base to choose best commercial composite material automatically, as illustrated in Figure 7. The output of wing structural design consultation from this expert system is shown in Figure 8.

4. CONCLUSIONS

An expert system approach to design of composite material wing structures is proposed in this paper. The initial development of a consultative expert system was presented. Currently,

COMPOSITE STRUCTURAL DESIGN

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You can choose the materials by following ways :
A. according to the application area
B. according to the requirement of material properties

A
B

1. Use the arrow keys or first letter of item to position the cursor.
2. Press RETURN/ENTER to continue.

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Figure 5. Two composite material selection approaches.

COMPOSITE STRUCTURAL DESIGN

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The proper fibers is CARBON/GRAPHITE_H.M (87%) CARBON/GRAPHITE_H.S (85%)
S-GLASS (83%)

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** End - RETURN/ENTER to continue

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COMPOSITE STRUCTURAL DESIGN

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The proper matrice is PEEK (85%) EPOXY (85%) POLYIMIDE (75%)

System will go into the dBase III Plus when you press RETURN key. In dBase
III Plus, you can enter the fiber material and matrix material, then system
will display the properties of all composites which are made by these fiber
and matrix

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** End - RETURN/ENTER to continue

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Figure 6. Conclusions from the material selection subsystem.

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--- COMPOSITE DATABASE ---

PROD_CODE   : Hy-E 2134A
PRODUCTER   : FIBERITE

MATRIX      : EPOXY 934
FIBER       : CARBON_H.M
COMPOSITE TYPE : UNIDIRECTIONAL TAPE

LONGITUDINAL TENSILE STRENGTH (MPa) : 1120.00
LONGITUDINAL TENSILE MODULUS (GPa)  : 231.00
LONGITUDINAL FLEXURAL STRENGTH (MPa) : 1276.00
LONGITUDINAL FLEXURAL MODULUS (GPa)  : 218.00

INTERLAMINATION SHEAR STRENGTH (Mpa) : .
TEMPERATURE - LONG TIME (F)          : .
TEMPERATURE - SHORT TIME (F)         : .

COST : FIBER VOLUMN : 60

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Figure 7. Material properties from the data base.

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COMPOSITE STRUCTURAL DESIGN

The proper wing structure is : SANDWICH_STRUCTURE (85%)
INTEGRATED_AIRFRAME_STRUCTURE (75%) Not CONVENTIONAL_AIRFRAME_STRUCTURE
(72%)

Press the RETURN key ,and system will show these figuresof wing structure to
you.

** End - RETURN/ENTER to continue

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Figure 8. Conclusions from the wing structural design subsystem.

this expert system can provide interactive aid in composite material selection and wing structural configuration arrangement. The future development tasks are focused on expanding the expert knowledge of wing structural design in the knowledge base and developing the failure mode prediction and design refinement subsystems.

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7. BIOGRAPHIES

Dr. J. L. Chen is currently on the faculty of the Department of Mechanical Engineering at the National Cheng Kung University, Tainan, Taiwan, Republic of China. His research interests include mechanical expert systems and structural optimization.

Dr. W.-C. Hwang is Deputy Head and Leader (Composite Design Group) within the Structural Section, 2nd division at the Chung Shan Institute of Science and Technology (CSIST), where he is responsible for composite design, analysis, testing, technical development and applications. Dr. Hwang has been with CSIST over 13 years. The areas of in-house research in which he involved were structural dynamics, solid propellant structural analysis, structural design analysis, and testing techniques for both metal and nonmetal structures.

Mr. S.-H. Sun is a graduate student in Department of Mechanical Engineering, National Cheng Kung University, Tainan, Taiwan, Republic of China.